

of Ganescu¹. Freshly prepared saturated solution of the compound in 50% aqueous ethanol was used.

Copper(II) solution : A standard solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving copper(II) sulphate (A.R.) in distilled water containing a little sulphuric acid. The metal content was determined by the cuprous thiocyanate method².

Diverse ions : Solutions of other ions were prepared from the chloride, nitrate or sulphate salts (A.R.) of cations and the metal contents were determined by conventional and standard methods².

Procedure for estimation of copper(II) : To an aliquot of standard solution containing 14-21 mg of copper(II), was added liquor ammonia (1 : 1) in slight excess to obtain a deep blue coloured copper-ammine complex. This solution was filtered (to remove insoluble hydroxides of other metals) and the reagent solution was added dropwise to precipitate out brownish pink coloured complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{PhNH}_2)_2]_2$. The precipitate was kept in an ice bath for 30 min (to avoid any loss due to solubility at room temperature) filtered through a weighed sintered or gooch crucible, washed successively with cold water containing few drops of reagent solution, 10% alcohol and finally with ether. The precipitate was dried at 105-110° to a constant weight. The precipitation is quantitative between pH 8.5-10.5 and 14 mg of copper can be successfully estimated with an accuracy of $\pm 0.33\%$.

Composition of the complex : The composition of the complex was determined from its analysis for copper, chromium and the isothiocyanate contents (found : Cu, 6.05 ; Cr, 9.56 ; NCS, 43.54% Calcd. for $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{PhNH}_2)_2]_2$: Cu, 5.93 ; Cr, 9.70 ; NCS, 43.32%) which correspond to the given formula.

Effect of diverse ions : Estimation of copper(II) can be successfully carried out in the presence of many common cations such as, Li^+ , Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Th^{4+} , Mn^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . However, the cations Ag^+ , Au^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Ir^{3+} , Ru^{3+} and Os^{4+} interfere in the estimation of copper(II) by this method. Interference by some metals, viz., Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Th^{4+} which form insoluble hydroxide is eliminated by filtration of the hydroxide prior to the precipitation of the complex. A double precipitation had to be done to remove the traces of adsorbed copper complex from the hydroxides.

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References

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